

What is CLIM4cities?

CLIM4cities is under a programme of, and funded by, the European Space Agency. Views expressed do not reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

CLIM4cities is an European Space Agency funded project made up of a team of experts from the Danish Meteorological Institute and CoLAB +ATLANTIC.

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In the face of a changing climate, cities are becoming increasingly exposed to extreme weather events.

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Extreme temperature events such as **heatwaves** are becoming longer, more frequent and intense in cities, affecting society's most vulnerable populations, as well as health and energy sectors.

Identifying vulnerable neighbourhoods within cities, projecting future climate scenarios, and understanding sector impacts from extreme temperature events are vital for addressing vulnerabilities, fostering resilience, and creating effective local adaptation strategies.

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CLIM4cities will address these needs by fostering Machine Learning and Citizen Science for heatwave prediction and spatial impact assessments in urban areas.

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CLIM4 CITIES

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